

Archaeoastronomy of Kukulcan Pyramid using an Squaring the Circle Construction Part I

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Abstract

Its show a diagram that represent a compass and straightedge construction to explain some interesting facts about Squaring the Circle and some astronomical facts about Kukulcan´s Pyramid. The manuscript is develop like a geometrical method to study architecture of ancient civilizations.

Keyword: Arqueoastronomy; Architecture; Maya

1 The Geometrical Method

Next diagram shows on 1 present a construction made with compass and straightedge used to obtain by vector projection; the identity (A):

$$Area_{Circle} = Area_{Square}$$

Geometrical methods are used frequently to identify astronomical facts about prehispanic architecture constructions.

While there no exist evidence about the development of some mathematical method to prove "Squaring the Circle" and specifically the identity (A) through history, its discovery like in ref [3] could help to reappraise the importance of some monuments and objects made by ancient cultures and its connection with mathematics; maybe beyond astronomy.

The diagram indicates on the points some sites of interest around "Kukulcan Pyramid" zone:

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Diagram 1. Squaring the Circle construction made with compass and straight-edge.

R = Virtual Point of Reference

S = Sun

P = Pleiades

T = Temple

V = Vertex of Pyramid

K = Start Point of Spring Equinox

Z = Zenith

Also shows two maps from Google Maps of the zone where Kukulcan Pyramid its settle.

Diagram 2. Map of Kukulcan's Pyramid by Google Maps.

Diagram 3. Map of Kukulcan's Pyramid by Google Maps.

Map on Google Maps

The square of the pyramid is taken as base to surpass such geometrical object with the square drawn on diagram 1.

In the words of the author of this manuscript; the next facts could be of inter-

est about the astronomy of the sun and the construction of Kukulkan Pyramid:

* The measures of the sides of the square that forms Kukulkan's Pyramid could be related with the measure of the sun radius.

* Such measure could be related with the number of stairs and structures found on Kukulkan's Pyramid.

* It is speculate that center of sun's circle; Pleiades position and some point on the intersection of an "approximate" trajectory of sun through Spring Equinox could be fundamental to place the first stages of construction of Kukulkan's Pyramid.

* Some points on diagram indicate a virtual place of interest where nowadays it is found part of another building structure but apparently are not connected with Kukulkan's building (point R).

The proposal made on this manuscript sustain the idea about the use of shadow projection through measurements made night and day to construct such architecture structure.

The facts about the number of stair and structures it hopes to be found through basic arithmetic operations; this assumption is based on ref[2].

Reference [3] make use mainly of mathematical vector methods. Through history there is no an exact date of its implementation like mathematical tool. Under the assumption that Mayan culture could make use of some similar diagram, they must be know some similar method by the epoch.

Its suggest on the research the reconstruction of diagram [1] using exact coordinates of astronomical objects obtained through the use of modern telescopes like could be the Large Milimeter Telescope to understand more about the geometry of such archaeological site and astronomical facts.

The diagram shows on [vector] only can be constructed on a computer; to obtain an exact match of sides length and angles to consider like true the identity between areas of square and circle; this fact can not appear on Kukulkan's Pyramid and its expected to be found being part of the architecture of Kukulkan's building in an approximate way.

Like part of this manuscript also its suggest research about the connection between the geometry of the diagram shows early and the existence of astronomical / geometrical facts assessed on ancient text (codex). Unfortunately the author of this manuscript lacks of resources or enough experience on the field of ancient Mayan text to provide more information or some clue about such facts. Only on reference [2] its mention a link between Mayan codex and mathematics;

and its expected that the use of diagrams like the proposed here; could be of use to help to decode more information about mathematics; specifically astronomy and geometry around such texts.

2 References

[1]Arqueoastronomía y Etnoastronomía en Mesoamérica; Editor: Broda, J.; Iwaniszewski, S.; Maupomé, L.; Instituto de Investigaciones Historicas; U.N.A.M. (1991). Chapter: Propiedades geométrico-astronómicas en la arquitectura prehipánica; Ponce de León; A.; page: 413.

[2]Las fascinantes, lúdicas y poderosas matemáticas de los mayas; Magaña; S. L. F; Secretaria de Educación; Gobierno del Estado de Yucatan (2012); ISBN: 978-607-95795-3-1

[3]Vector Projection of a Construction Made with a Rule and Compass to Understand Squaring the Circle; M. Díaz; J. Rodrigo A.; <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3854105/v2> (preprint 2024)